

TEST QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT ON SELECTED TOPICS IN CALCULUS 1

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to create and validate a midterm test questionnaire for Calculus 1, tailored for 2nd-year Bachelor of Secondary Education students majoring in Mathematics at Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology. As an instrumentation study, it involved creating a 100-item multiple-choice test based on the official syllabus. The test was reviewed by three experts for refinement and by 15 student validators for its structural soundness. The validity of the test was determined to be nearly perfect and highly acceptable. It was subsequently pilot-tested with 81 4th-year BSEd Mathematics students and subjected to item analysis, including evaluations of the difficulty index, discrimination index, and reliability. The test achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.81, demonstrating strong internal consistency. These results indicate that the developed test is an effective tool for classroom assessment.

Keywords: *Test Questionnaire Development, Validation, Item Analysis, Mathematics Education*

INTRODUCTION

A strong foundation in Calculus 1 is essential for success in subsequent calculus courses and real-world applications. However, students, especially future mathematics teachers, often face significant challenges in calculus due to ambiguously worded exams, which hinder their ability to demonstrate knowledge (Fatimah & Yerizon, 2019; Brown & Knight,

1994). Unclear language, vague terms, and lack of context in exam questions can lead to student confusion and incorrect answers that may not accurately reflect their understanding (Schoenfeld, 1992). Additionally, unclear instructions can prevent students from applying appropriate problem-solving strategies, disadvantaging those with weaker language skills and undermining the assessment's validity.

Preparing a test questionnaire is an important step while conducting educational research, which must be carefully planned so that it may state correctly about the cognitive gains. In test development—not only is operationalizing the construct vital but a well-designed plan upfront regarding what we are assessing—is key to valid findings (Irwing & Hughes, 2018; Lane et al., 2016). A table of specifications is an instrument to ensure the test harmony with learning objectives and also can stress thinking skills (Fives & Barnes, 2013; Retno et al., 2019). It includes item creation, expert review, pilot testing, data analysis, and a host of other activities to establish the reliability of the test. It has been well-documented that higher-order thinking skills are difficult to measure (DeBarger et al., 2016; Mamolo, 2019), and models for creating effective tests in the context of validation have been proposed.

Exam questions should be straightforward and explicit to promote equal evaluation. To guarantee fairness, educators should thoroughly evaluate and pilot-test these questions (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). Calculus learning that is both successful and accurate depends on a well-designed and tested test questionnaire. Since content, format, and accuracy are crucial for test validity, Kline (2005) emphasizes the serious risks associated with depending on invalidated instruments. Furr (2021) highlights the detrimental effects of poorly constructed questionnaires, pointing out that in the absence of appropriate validation protocols, educators frequently have imprecise notions of what constitutes a good evaluation. A well-crafted and verified test questionnaire in calculus not only guarantees accurate evaluation but also propels student advancement and informs focused training. Such evaluations are essential for recognizing learning issues and directing effective training, as suggested by Black and William (2018). Validity and reliability are essential for an accurate and fair assessment (Taherdoost, 2016; Kara & Çelikler, 2015).

Regarding questionnaire development, the school is still in its infancy, especially in mathematics education. As a result, the motivation behind this project is to develop and validate questions measuring specific topics on the Calculus 1 midterm exam. We aim to assist with the evaluation process by providing teachers with some useful tools for evaluation. These surveys will help teachers identify if any students need more attention, keep a check and balance on students' performance, and understand what all the comprehension or understanding of things are. In the end, it aims to advance our field of educational evaluation as a whole.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to develop and validate the test questionnaire for the Calculus 1 midterm. Specially, it sought to answer the following:

1. develop a midterm test questionnaire on selected topics on Calculus 1 based on the domains of Revised Bloom's taxonomy.
2. determine the validity of the developed test questionnaire;
3. determine the reliability of the developed test questionnaire.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed instrumentation to develop and validate test questionnaires that include midterm topics in Calculus 1, following the approved syllabus. Instrumentation research includes testing, developing, and applying measurements including questionnaires (Biddix, 2018). The focus of instrumentation research works on composing the items properly which effectively measures what it is intended to measure; this does not only mean that these tools have to be valid but also reliable. These include clearness of the items, content validity to verify whether an instrument covers all essential features of a construct, and scoring consistency (Kline 2005).

Research Instrument

This study utilized an adapted instrument to assess the developed Calculus 1 midterm test questionnaire. The content validity, face validity, and reliability coefficient tools are from Oducado (2020), Desai and Patel (2020), and Longe and Maharaj (2023) respectively. Face validity is determined using a yes/no approach to assess if items measure intended concepts, while content validity is evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale. Scales utilized in this study are presented in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6.

Table 1. Interpretation and Acceptability of % of Agreement (Face Validity)

% of agreement	Strength of Agreement per question or overall	Action for each Question / entire tool
< 80	Poor	Restructure
80 - 90	Substantial	Substantial Revise
90 - 100	Full	Retain

Table 2. Content Validity Interpretation

Mean Range	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very High	Very much acceptable
3.41 – 4.20	High	Acceptable
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	Moderately Acceptable
1.81 – 2.60	Low	Slightly Acceptable
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	Not acceptable

Table 3. Reliability Coefficient Interpretation

Reliability	Interpretation
0.90 and above	Excellent
0.80 - 0.89	Good
0.70 – 0.79	Average
0.60 – 0.69	Questionable
0.50 – 0.59	Poor
0.50 or below	Unacceptable

Table 4. Index of Difficulty (P-Values)

P-value range	Interpretation
0.00 – 0.20	Very Difficult Item
0.21 – 0.40	Difficult Item
0.41 – 0.60	Moderately Difficult Item
0.61 – 0.80	Easy Item
0.81 and above	Very Easy item

(Padua & Santos, 1997)

Table 5. Index of Discrimination (D-Index).

D value range	Interpretation
-1.00 – -0.60	Questionable Item
-0.59 - -0.21	Not Discriminating
-0.20 – 0.20	Moderately discriminating
0.21 – 0.59	Discriminating
0.60 – 1.00	Very Discriminating

(Padua & Santos, 1997)

Table 6. The Decision for Discrimination Index and Difficulty Index.

Discrimination Index (D-Value)	Difficulty Index (P-Value)	Decision
Acceptable	Acceptable	Retained
Not Acceptable	Acceptable	Revised
Acceptable	Not Acceptable	Revised
Not Acceptable	Not Acceptable	Rejected

(Padua & Santos, 1997)

Process in the Development of Test Questionnaire

This research adapted the Development and Validation Design utilized by Mamolo (2021), which included four stages: conceptualization, development of the test, trial of the

test, and testing. This study involved conceptualizing, developing, validating, and pilot testing.

Conceptualization

The initial step was to determine the relevant concepts for the selected midterm topics in Calculus 1. When creating the midterm test, the items were constructed to represent each concept based on the syllabus. The identified topics in midterm Calculus 1 are conics, limits and continuity, fundamentals of derivatives, derivatives of trigonometric and inverse trigonometric functions, derivatives of hyperbolic and inverse hyperbolic functions, and applications of derivatives. This is based on the approved syllabus of the Institution and considering CMO No. 75 series 2017, Policies Standard and Guidelines.

Development of the Test

This phase involves creating a table of specifications based on the syllabus covering midterm topics and afterward drafting test items. The number of items per topic is based on the number of teaching hours with its respective percentage. The conics with 8 hours; the limits and continuity 8; fundamentals of derivatives 4; derivative of trigonometric and inverse trigonometric functions 4; derivative of hyperbolic and inverse hyperbolic functions 4; and applications of derivatives 4. There are 25 items on each topic of conics and limits (Item Number 1 – 50), 13 item questions each for fundamentals of derivatives and derivatives of trigonometric and inverse trigonometric functions (Item Number 51 - 76). Lastly, 12-item questions each on the topic of the derivative of hyperbolic and inverse hyperbolic functions and applications of derivatives (Item Number 77 – 100).

After crafting the test, it undergoes many reviews and refinement. Scoring guidelines and completeness criteria were also established. Some test items are derived from previous questionnaires and utilize a multiple-choice format appropriate for the assessed year level. The test questionnaire encompasses questions of varying difficulty levels.

Validation of the Test Questionnaire

The Calculus 1 midterm test questionnaire was then validated by three experts, with at least a master's degree and three years of teaching experience. This process followed Gilbert and Prion's (2016) guidelines, where the involvement of three experts provided acceptable evidence of content validity. The validators were provided with TOS, course syllabus, and validation tool.

In addition, 15 fourth-year BSEd-Mathematics students measured the test face validity after the pilot testing phase. These students were purposively and randomly selected among the test takers. They look at the structure of the questionnaire to ensure its significance and effectiveness, contributing to the overall quality of the test.

Pilot Testing

The test questionnaire was administered to 81 fourth-year Mathematics education students after the validation. The pilot testing was designed to evaluate the quality of specific test items, the total effectiveness of the test, and the suitability of the test's structure (Syahfitri et al., 2019).

Subsequently, an item analysis was done to gauge the difficulty and discrimination index of each test item. This process helped the identification of problematic items needing revision or removal. Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20) was utilized to determine its internal consistency and reliability (Bobbit, 2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Validity of the Test

The expert valuation of the Calculus 1 midterm test questionnaire revealed a good content validity, with an overall mean score of 4.00 which implies a high level of agreement among experts about its conformity to the intended construct. Also, it means that the questionnaire accurately and comprehensively measures what is aimed at (Haynes et al., 1995). This score scale implies that the test items well fit into the assessment objectives and content displaying experts' consensus on their relevance (Lynn, 1986; Cook & Beckman, 2006).

High content validity is pivotal for the effectiveness and relevance of tests since it ensures chances that the questionnaire will result in correct and significant outcomes. Recent studies emphasize that powerful content validity increases the credibility and reliability of an evaluative tool hence making it important to researchers as well as practitioners (Thompson, 2023). The expert assessments confirmed that the test elements were properly representing their domains which is paramount for its overall validity and utility.

Furthermore, an analysis of the questionnaire's face validity was conducted referring to how it looks from the perspective of those taking it. The face validity received a 95% rating which means that the test content is clear and follows the course objectives (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Bolarinwa, 2015). This high rating is important because this infers that students would deal with it much more seriously leading to less anxious situations thus improving accuracy levels (Simonson et al., 2021; Sireci & Benítez, 2023). In addition, students' involvement in the validation process is a good practice when doing educational assessments (Lane 2014).

Item Analysis

For the Calculus 1 midterm test, table 7 indicates the item difficulty levels; this is an important measure of the extent to which each question is difficult for students. In

assessments, item difficulty which is the fraction of students answering a question correctly, is essential to maintain overall fairness and balance (Siregar et al., 2023). This metric provides insight into how one can design an exam that suitably stretches the students while also representing their actual capabilities.

The test items were categorized according to the level of difficulty, with 9 very difficult items, 15 difficult, 10 moderately difficult, 9 easy, and 27 very easy. This distribution shows there is a wide range of difficulty which is crucial for us to develop a more complete assessment. The presence of 24 very difficult and difficult items is especially helpful in distinguishing between students who possess a better understanding of the material and those that require further assistance (Miller et al., 2021). These difficult items assess individuals at higher levels of understanding as well as problem-solving ability hence making them significant in testing high-performing students (Anderson et al., 2001).

The enclosure of 36 very-easy and easy items guarantees that students can access the test at their level, giving them an opportunity to showcase what they know (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). At the same time, 10 questions of moderate difficulty serve to strike a balance so that no one is mainly treated as either normal or above normal in these tests. With a balanced distribution, everyone has an equal chance, which leads to a true representation of student performance based on it (Kline, 2005; Simoson et al., 2021).

Table 7. Item Difficulty of the Test Questionnaire

Difficulty Index	Frequency	Percentage	Test Item Number/s	Verbal Interpretation
0.00 – 0.20	9	13%	36, 39, 40, 48, 49, 54, 66, 77, 100	Very Difficult Item
0.21 – 0.40	15	19%	11, 16, 45, 56, 60, 61, 63, 68, 70, 71, 76, 79, 80, 94, 97	Difficult Item
0.41 – 0.60	10	17%	3, 5, 8, 13, 22, 23, 35, 82, 84, 88	Moderately Difficult Item
0.61 – 0.80	9	13%	4, 10, 12, 34, 50, 62, 65, 81, 95,	Easy Item
0.81 and above	27	38%	1, 2, 7, 15, 20, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, 32, 37, 43, 44, 46, 47, 51, 42, 53, 55, 72, 87, 92, 93, 96, 98, 99	Very Easy item
Total	70	100%	70	

Table 8 summarizes the item discrimination in the Calculus 1 midterm examination, which is often regarded as a significant part of educational assessment. Item discrimination indicates whether test items can effectively distinguish between students who have high scores and those who do not. When the level of item discrimination is high, it shows its ability to separate these two groups constituting a good quality test (Cohen & Swerdlik, 2009).

The analysis showed that there are different levels of discrimination among the test items. Five items were distinguished as being very discriminating, which means they are efficient in differentiating those who understand the content from those who do not. Such items greatly improve both the validity and reliability of a given exam (Kelley & Preacher, 2019). Moreover, 26 discriminating items can effectively separate various performances, which significantly adds to the general reliability of this test (Muñiz & Fonseca-Pedrero, 2019).

Most of the test items (34) had moderate levels of discrimination thus providing sensible differentiation. In general, these items are not as precise as the highly discriminating ones but they still contribute positively towards students' performance assessment (Osterlind, 2010). However, five items were found to have marginal discrimination signifying that they did not distinguish effectively among students' abilities. In order not to compromise the overall reliability of the tests and also ensure an accurate measure of students' understanding, it may be necessary to revise or replace such low-discrimination items (Downing, 2003).

Table 8. Item Discrimination of the Test Questionnaire

Difficulty Index	Frequency	Percentage	Test Item Number/s	Verbal Interpretation
-1.00 – -0.60	5	7%	27, 43, 62, 63, 70	Questionable Item
-0.59 - -0.21	0	0%	0	Not Discriminating
-0.20 – 0.20	34	49%	1, 2, 11, 15, 16, 20, 26, 29, 30, 14, 37, 39, 40, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 61, 66, 68, 72, 92, 93, 94, 95, 98	Moderately discriminating
0.19 – 0.59	26	37%	3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 12, 13, 32, 35, 36, 56, 60, 65, 77, 79, 80, 81, 82, 84, 87, 88, 96, 97, 99, 100	Discriminating
0.60 – 1.00	5	7%	22, 24, 34, 71, 76	Very Discriminating
Total	70	100%	70	

Table 9 shows that out of the 70 items in the Calculus 1 test questionnaire, 23 were appropriate for inclusion in the final version. They met the expectations of being impartial and difficult enough to assist in making a distinction between high achievers and low achievers, as well as being challenging (Kline, 2005). Hence, the preservation of these items is key in upholding an equitable and consistent assessment that quantitatively indicates the essential content areas and performance levels.

On the contrary, 12 items were flagged for revision because of discrimination ability or difficulty problems. The items were inappropriate for inclusion in the final test in their

current form (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). Consequently, there is a need to revise these items so that they can be clearer and more effective about the test's aims and also serve as better measures of student knowledge.

Furthermore, 35 items were disqualified because they were found to have serious weaknesses concerning their discrimination, difficulty, or both. An item that is too difficult or too easy, or if it does not discriminate effectively between low and top performers, does not contribute valuable information to the overall assessment and can undermine the reliability and validity of the test. The removal of such items is pivotal for maintaining the quality and fairness of the test as they may incorporate bias and inaccuracies (Cook & Beckman, 2006). It is important to carefully select and revise test items based on discrimination and difficulty indices so that a fair and reliable assessment tool can be developed that measures what it was designed to measure reliably to enhance education outcomes (Miller et al., 2021).

Table 9. Summary of Item Analysis for the test questionnaire in Calculus 1 (Midterm)

Final Evaluation/Remark	Frequency	Percentage	Item Number/s
Items to be Retained	23	33%	3, 4, 5, 8, 10, 13, 22, 23, 34, 35, 45, 50, 56, 60, 65, 71, 76, 79, 80, 82, 84, 88, 97
Items to be Revised	12	17%	7, 12, 16, 31, 36, 61, 63, 68, 77, 81, 96, 100
Items to be Rejected	35	50%	1, 2, 11, 15, 20, 26, 27, 29, 30, 32, 37, 39, 40, 43, 44, 46, 47, 48, 49, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 62, 66, 70, 72, 87, 92, 93, 94, 95, 98, 99
Total	70	100%	70

Reliability of the Test

The validated Calculus 1 midterm examination was pilot-tested to 81 fourth-year mathematics students. An item analysis was then carried out to help ensure that there were no items on the test that had poor correlations. At first, a reliability coefficient of 0.49 was observed, indicating that there was a low level of internal consistency among the test items (Kline, 2005). It was noted that 30 items had bad correlations which meant they did not accurately measure what they were supposed to measure hence these were deleted from the examination.

Reliability analysis was done on 70 items that had remained after the elimination of 30 poor-performing items. This adjustment led to a significant increase in the KR-20 value, which rose to 0.81. KR20 is used for measuring the internal consistency of dichotomous tests such as true-false or multiple-choice tests (Crocker & Algina, 2008). Therefore it is essential for educational testing reliability assessment. Overall test reliability was

enhanced as poor-performing items were removed; these were items that did not discriminate between different students' performance levels well enough and were either too hard or too easy.

The improvement of reliability is important because it allows for test results to be consistent and accurate across different times it is administered. Also, it shows that there is a likelihood that similar results will come up when the tool is used on diverse groups of learners who have similar levels of abilities thus supporting its validity (Furr, 2021). A major approach followed in modifying the examination through the removal of poorly functioning items is guaranteed to make sure that the evaluation measures what it intends to measure and does so reliably.

Conclusions

The test questionnaire on Calculus 1 was constructed based on the approved syllabus topics. The test quality and its validity were checked through the creation of a Table of Specifications (TOS) based on Revised Bloom's Taxonomy. This test evaluation shows that there is strong content validity since the ratings are within the "acceptable" range and thus the items are relevant and representative of subject matter. In addition, the face validity score for this test was "full" which means it is an accurate representation of the content intended to be measured, thus confirming that questions truly reflect all desired learning outcomes.

As indicated by the findings, the Calculus 1 midterm assessment shows a variety of item difficulties and levels of discrimination that influence the test's general effectiveness. The exam contained many easy and very easy items which may result in disparity in testing advanced students at different levels of proficiency. In this regard, the discrimination analysis showed that there are items that discriminate highly, moderately, or hardly respectively. This means that some of the questions are good at separating students with varying abilities while others are not good at distinguishing between them.

A decision to keep 23 items, modify 12 items, and eliminate 35 items from the final test denoted a commitment to improving its validity and reliability. Retaining the most effective items guarantees a solid basis of reliable measures whereas revising and excluding various items show an attempt at enhancing the general quality of the test. By carefully selecting and modifying according to difficulty and discrimination indices, such that students will have their understanding better assessed through the final test whose results provide important feedback on learning outcomes. This process of continual improvement follows recommended practices in education assessment which help in making sure that this examination is just and also effective in distinguishing diverse degrees or levels of student performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings there are some recommendations on the way to improve the quality of the assessment tool. It is important to carry out regular item analyses for forthcoming

versions of the test. This helps identify and delete items that have poor correlation with total test scores helping to maintain internal consistency and reliability of the assessment. The general quality of the test is retained by only including items that correctly measure the intended constructs.

Continuous validation studies are necessary for them to corroborate the test's reliability and validity among various populations. Even though acceptable marks were obtained from the validation, using the test in larger and more varied samples could offer more proof of the effectiveness of the assessment tool. In this respect, persistent validation is crucial in justifying its application and keeping it nonbiased within greater student pools.

Changing items that perform poorly is another priority. The new items should be subjected to a rigorous process of testing and review before they are included in the test to ensure that it remains wide-ranging and reflect the totality of learning competencies spelled out in the syllabus. This ensures high levels of reliability and validity on the part of the test over an extended period.

It is recommended that teachers be offered training in the crafting of valid tests. Training educators on how to write clear, concise, and valid test items could lead to quality assessment. In addition, incorporating feedback mechanisms that allow students to report on any ambiguities or difficulties during the test can provide valuable information for further improvement. This way, students are involved in their assessment process to make it more comprehensive and highlight areas that need adjustments.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research was conducted adhering to proper ethical standards and as well as strictly complying with all guidelines set by institutions and laws.

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